

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.23 Second Dissemination workshop results

Public

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1. Summary

This document is a part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Work Package (WP6). The goal of the deliverable D6.23 “Second Dissemination workshop results” is to summarize the 2nd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event which was held online on 21st of September 2023.

2. Introduction

The project dissemination activities are mainly focused on network extension and sharing of the results internally and among the identified external stakeholders and audience of interest. Thus, the project should have an understandable stakeholders’ engagement approach to amplify the results and activities of other members of the cybercrime ecosystem – helping to maximise impact and positive change in the fight against different forms of cybercrime.

The CYCLOPES network stakeholder audience are defined as follows:

Audience 1: Practitioners (i.e. LEAs) interested in the uptake of security research and innovation in relation to the fight against cybercrime. All CYCLOPES partners engage practitioners throughout the project timeframe by inviting relevant stakeholders to the projects’ events and workshops, by proposing that they take part in different initiatives and ask for their feedback on how CYCLOPES solutions can support enhanced resilience to cybercrime.

Audience 2: Industry including SMEs. CYCLOPES engage industry players having interests in fighting cybercrime. This network is invited to participate in the CYCLOPES events, workshops and webinars and receives all supportive documents needed to actively participate in key activities.

Audience 3: Scientific community. CYCLOPES results and updates are delivering to the relevant EU and Member State organisations such as Universities, Research and Technology Organisations, research communities and institutes, as well as the private sector.

Audience 4: Policymakers. CYCLOPES identify and proactively contact with targeted audience and invite interested actors to the projects’ events and workshops. CYCLOPES reach policymakers on both a European (i.e. DG Home, DG Connect, DG Grow) and on Member State level.

Throughout the duration of the project, CYCLOPES intends to build and sustain efficient audience relations in order to enable interaction between differing innovation parties, and build synergies with already established European, and national networks of practitioners.

3. 2nd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event

3.1. Main goal of the event

The dissemination is a fundamental activity to create project visibility and reach various target groups. Efficient dissemination during the CYCLOPES project ensures short and long-term success and through yearly Dissemination Events, CYCLOPES ensures that:

- Project outputs and outcomes are widely disseminated to the right target audiences.
- Stakeholders can contribute to the output’s development, evaluation and exploitation. Thus, they should be identified and encouraged from the beginning to proactively interact with the consortium partners on a systematic basis.

A crucial part of dissemination events is to present the main project findings to a large spectrum of stakeholders and ensure efficient interaction between CYCLOPES and relevant partners. These events foster network activities, raise awareness of the project and bring together relevant practitioners and stakeholders who may wish to join to the CYCLOPES network and its activities.

3.2. Summary of the event

On the 21st of September 2023, the 2nd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event was held online to stimulate dialogue on pressing security matters and crime issues. 99 people registered for the event, and the final audience consisted of 74 people from LEAs across Europe, industry and science as well as relevant networks and organisations responsible for fighting cybercrime.

At the beginning, Rashel Talukder, the CYCLOPES Project Coordinator, opened the event and presented the scope of the project. Then, leaders of particular work packages presented the current activities and those planned in the near future. The presentations were given by representatives of:

- Home Office, UK
- Centre of Excellence in Terrorism, Resilience, Intelligence and Organised Crime Research (CENTRIC), UK
- Austrian Standards International (ASI), Austria
- Cybercrime Research Institute (CRI), Germany
- Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS), Poland

Figure 1 CYCLOPES online Dissemination Event 2023

4. Conclusion

This document summaries the 2nd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event which aim was to reflect on the CYCLOPES activities that took place during the second year of the project implementation.

Overall, the event was a success with insightful presentations that gave an insight into the progress that has been made, and the aspects to improve on going forward. The 3rd CYCLOPES Dissemination Event is planned for April 2024. This event will serve as a platform for cyber-related activities to share their work and engage practitioners. The ultimate goal will be to create several tracks and parallel activities (e.g. workshops, technology presentations, discussion panels) that cater to various needs – covering the practical solutions available to respond to the latest trends, the strategic planning and tactics required to equip European law enforcement with the necessary competencies and capabilities to deal with emerging threats.